

Supporting Information

Room-Temperature Film Formation of Metal Halide Perovskites on n-type Metal Oxides: The Catalysis of ZnO on Perovskite Crystallization

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EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials and Synthesis:

ITO substrates were all purchased from Shenzhen Huayu Union Technology Co. Ltd. Methylammonium iodide (CH₃NH₃I) powder was purchased from Dyesol Limited. Poly[(9,9-dioctylfluorenyl-2,7-diyl)-co-(4,4'-(N-(4-sec-butylphenyl)diphenylamine))] (TFB) was supplied by Lumtec. Ltd. 2-isopropanol (HPLC, 99.9%), ethanol (anhydrous, 99.8%), lead iodide (PbI₂, 99.99%), Toluene (99.9%), Polyethylenimine (PEIE) 80% ethoxylated solution, Zinc acetate dihydrate (99.999%), N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.9%) were all purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Tin(IV) oxide (SnO₂) 15% in H₂O colloidal dispersion was purchased from Alfa Aesar. PEIE was dispersed in IPA solution with a concentration of 0.05 wt %. All the materials were used as received without any further purification. ZnO nanocrystals, SnO₂ and TiO_x solution were prepared as previous reported.^[1-3] The precursor solution of perovskite halide with a concentration of 1.0 M of PbI₂, were prepared by mixing CH₃NH₃I with PbI₂ powder with 2:1 molar ration in DMF. The solution was stirred at 60 °C over 2 h and filtered with a 0.45 μm filter before use.

Film and device fabrication process:

All the ITO coated glass substrates were treated with detergent overnight and then by TL1 (NH₃: H₂O₂: H₂O = 1:1:5) procedure for 20 min prior to dry them at high-speed nitrogen flow. TiO_x, SnO₂ and ZnO films were all deposited in ambient condition and annealed at 150 °C for 15 mins. Perovskite films were spin-coated on the substrates in glovebox (under room light) at 5000 r.p.m for 45 s. 120 μL toluene was quickly dropped on the substrate 5 s after starting the spin coating process. For the vacuum dried perovskite devices, the film was placed into the vacuum chamber for 12 h at 0.1 Bar (in the dark condition) under dark. TFB (8 mg/ml in CB) were prepared by spin-coating corresponding solution onto perovskite film. The device fabrication processes were finished by depositing 8 nm MoO₃ film and 100 nm Ag film as electrode inside of the thermal evaporator. The device working area is 0.0725 cm². For the ZnO/PEIE based films, the PEIE was coated and annealed at 100 °C for 10 min in the glovebox.

Film and device characterizations:

The SEM images were obtained by FEI (Quanta 200 FEG) scanning electron microscopy. For the absorption measurements and XRD, all the samples are covered with a ~100 nm layer of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). UV-Vis absorption spectra are obtained with PerkinElmer Lambda 900. Steady state PL spectra were obtained with a 485 nm laser and an Andor spectrometer. The XRD spectrum of perovskite film was performed using a PANalytical Empyrean system. Perovskite LED devices were all measured in a nitrogen-filled glovebox at room temperature. A Keithley 2400 was used to collect current density and driving voltage data and an integrating sphere together with the Go pro spectrometer (Ocean Optics) were used to collect emission data.